

A Detailed Review Study on Energy/Power Efficient Routing Protocols for Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks

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Abstract:

In ocean traveling applications, such as ocean tracking, harmful substances detection, sea activity of the capital, etc., Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UASNs) have become more important. The peculiar features and movement of under water acoustic channels galvanized the development of the routing protocols for underwater settings in order to establish the underwater applications possible. In the last two decades, various routing methods have been introduced and strategies introduced to achieve the network's energy efficiency and lifespan. This survey paper classifies all routing protocols into different classes and classifies routing strategies according to their properties. The main focus of this paper is on two different types of protocols: I spatial protocols for routing and (ii) hybrid protocols for routing. In addition, some protocols offer network lifetime, end-to-end delay and supply ratio for development of USN routing protocols. The protocols also say various types of techniques for achieving the energy efficiency in specific underwater sensor network situations.

Keywords: acoustic sensor networks, routing protocol, power consumption, energy efficiency, network lifetime, location information, depth information

1. INTRODUCTION

About 71 percent of our earth's atmosphere is covered by water. The thick sea on this planet is an enormous and largely unknown ecosystem. The ocean and even research can not be tracked in deep water. As a result, wireless sensor networks and their implementations will replace ocean exploration and monitoring methods. The UASN is one of the broad research areas for monitoring and collecting various types of data for environmental studies. The UASNs have been of great significance in ocean exploration activities in recent decades. In UASNs, the underwater environment doesn't permit radio frequency (RF) waves; it empowers active sound waves to communicate with one another instead of RF waves [1]. Power management, energy management and the development of a routing protocol are a major challenge for UWSNs. Two definitions exist in the UWSNs: deep water and soft water. The depth of the ocean in shallow water is less than 100 m, while the ocean's depth is less profound[2].

Many routing protocols even challenge the conception of the routing protocol for (UWSNs) in terrestrial wireless sensor networks (TWSN). Some problems with the design of routing protocols include: (1) communication bandwidth is small, (2) propagation delay is high and (3) the higher bit error ratio; Location information in UWSNs is not easily obtained due to water streams and mobility problems in floating node areas. The paper focuses mainly on the production and energy efficiency of routing protocols at UWSN. Displaying different routing protocols from previous UWSN studies, the routing protocols were divided into two categories: regional routing protocol and hybrid routing protocol. Energy efficiency here depends mainly on the metrics to be calculated while the protocol is being built.

2. RELATED WORK

This paper focused primarily on the study of UWSN technical energy efficiency. UWSN protocol routing is categorized in two categories: geographical (locational details of sensor nodes forwarded as packets from source to sink) and hybrid (energy- and geographic) routing protocols.

2.1. GEOGRAPHIC-BASED ROUTING PROTOCOLS

The primary goal of the protocol on the geographical routing is to decide on the role. The packet transmissions in mobile and sensor networks in hostile environments are promising [3]. This protocol focuses mainly on routing performance and requires no topological routing performance (one hop)[4]. Geographical routing, which requires lower memories for nodes which maintain information locally[5], is more analytical for larger networks than topological routing. The following geographic routing protocols use different policies to adopt and select the next hop [6].

- a. All the existing geographic routing protocols are used for 2D networks, but UWSN are deployed for 3D networks.
- b. It does not consider the reliability issue (node failure due to single forwarding path).
- c. Different policies are based on stability of network topologies.

A. DBR (Depth Based Routing Protocol)

Depth Simple Routing is a type of geographic routing protocol and is entirely focused on knowledge of the depth of nodes in submarine sensors. DBR[7][8]'s key benefit is its multi-sink system. The example of this network is shown in Figure 1.

DBR uses a brutal strategy to send items to the sink on the top of the submarine. It concentrates only depth data that can be easily measured by the sensor nodes. DBR normally provides a protocol based on information on the depth of a sensor node. Additional details, such as energy level and distance from nearby nodes, can be implemented to take routing decisions to reduce energy costs and grid life. Only a high packing supply ratio with lower energy is possible in dense networks with simulation results of DBR. Greedy is not here to improve the performance of fragmented networks. In order to achieve improved performance, higher energy efficiency and distribution rates, better deployments and advanced recovery algorithms should be used for several sinking networks.

Figure 1. Multiple-sink UWSNs Architecture

B. AMCTD (Adaptive Mobility of Courier nodes in Threshold-optimized Depth-based Routing Protocol)

AMCTD routing protocol mainly focuses on the network lifetime of UWSN. In the previous protocol it concentrates only depth based sensor nodes but the network lifetime and the energy consumption is the main

acquisition due to unnecessary data forwarding. This raises the problem of stability, energy consumption and worst throughput during unequal load distribution among the sensor nodes. To overcome this issue AMCTD routing protocol proposed some phases [9] as follows:

First Phase (Network Initialization): Weighted network density based on each node and designed corresponding node movement.

Second Phase (Data Forwarding): Forwarders decide to prioritize optimal weights based on neighboring source nodes.

Third Step (Depth Threshold): network prioritization of depth weights is allocated and energy is adjusted according to the sparse network environment.

Fourth Phase (Movement of Courier Nodes): Threshold Nodes are designed to address network sparseness due to movement of courier nodes and depth variations.

Using this protocol, low-sensor node energy consumption decreases to achieve stability. It provides network load balance and offers a detailed time estimate to the source nodes neighbor. Messaging node movement finally gives network passage (metrics) in sparse network environment. The loss of high transmission in AMCTD is due to distant transmissions of medium depth nodes, and in particular the mobility pattern of courier nodes[10] is not ideal for sensitive information applications.

In iAMTCD [10], (Improved Adaptive mobility of courier nodes in threshold-optimized depth-based routing) routing protocol is succeeded for the above said problems and gives the better solutions as follow:

- a. F_{FS} calculation technique enhanced and maximized the lifetime of reactive UWSNs.
- b. Minimizes end-to-end packet delay for delay-sensitive applications in sparse networks.
- c. Minimize the data loss in delay-sensitive applications and increase the number of eligible neighbours due to variation in depth threshold.

C. MRP (Mobicast Routing Protocol)

Mobicast is also referred to as mobile geocast (Mobile Geocast [11]), the underwater sensor nodes of this protocol are distributed by USN (USN) 3D (Three Dimensional). The main goal is to solve all problems and to minimize sensor node energy use and to optimize 3D USN data collection. AUV or mobile sink nodes are a 3D ZOR (Reference Zone). AUV (Autonomous Underwater Vehicle). AUV continuously records the data collection in 3D zorrns at various times on the user-defined path. Data collection. The sensor nodes of 3D ZOR are normally long-term in sleep mode. The goal of this protocol is to obtain data from sensor nodes 3D ZOR efficiently. Two phases depend on the MRP;

- a. Collect the data from 3D ZOR sensor nodes.
- b. Trying to avoid topology holes while wake up the sensor nodes in the next 3D ZOR.

Power-saving Mobicast protocol is developed for 3D whole problem in 3D USN by using the technique called 'apple slice'. This technique is used to build the multiple segments around a hole to assure that the route path is clear and continuity. Hence, the performance analysis shows the improvement of delivery rate and power consumption. MRP have an advantage to find and get the data continuously in 3D ZOR with apple slice

technique to achieve power-saving Mobicast protocol, but the problem is difficult to measure the performance metrics with apple slice technique and the energy consumption is not stabilized correctly.

D. H²-DAB (Hop-by-Hop Dynamic Address Based Routing Protocol)

Recent routing schemes for UWSNs require additional nodes and special hardware sort to maximize data load. In geographic routing protocols full-dimensional location information was required. Having localization information in UWSNs is not so simple, so you need some location-conscious methods. H2-DAB was used for multi-sink architecture to solve the issues. It has some significant advantages[12],

- a. No special hardware, no new type of nodes and no extra cost*
- b. Not require full-dimensional information*
- c. Not to maintain complex routing tables*
- d. Easily handled node movements with water currents*
- e. Take full advantage of multi-sink architecture*

H²-DAB tries to keep the minimum routing overheads, as available data rates are extremely low for UWSN. The idea of this protocol is to follow per-contact routing, instead of per-hop routing according to the underwater requirements. In H²-DAB, delivery ratios are not considered seriously based on density of sensor nodes. Finally, it delivers high delivery ration (nearly 90%) in both the networks (dense & sparse) with low delays and energy consumptions.

E. GEDAR (Geographic and Opportunistic routing with Depth Adjustment-based topology control for communication Recovery)

GEDAR is a whatevercast, spatial and opportunistic protocol seeking to relay a packet from a source node to a few sonobuoys[13]. In this protocol, greedy approach is used to forward the packet in each hop put in the sonobuoys. If the data packet is trapped in a void node, it relies on the depth change of the node. The main purpose of this protocol is to find node location information, neighbor node, sonobuoys to continue the forwarding packet to other sonobuoys using greedy forwarding methodology. Even this protocol recognizes any underwater routing set by using several sonobuoys as sink nodes.

Each sonobuoy at the ocean surface is furnished with a GPS (Global Positioning System) [14], they utilizes occasional beaconing to spread its area data to the submerged sensor nodes. Hence, it is called as location in USN. The location of the neighbour nodes is also known as occasional beaconing. To gain the effects of acoustic channels GEDAR acts as OR (Opportunistic Routing). In OR, a subset of neighbour nodes are determined to continue the forwarding strategy to some sonobuoy. The main focus and challenge of OR is to select the next-hop forwarder for list their neighbour nodes, due to this process it reduces the terminal problems. It selects most qualified candidate neighbours with the consideration of GEDAR position mechanism called next-hop forwarder selection. GEDAR is achieved the data routing in UWSN and take full pros to the broadcast communications for forwarding data packet to the surface sonobuoys. Mainly, it controls the void nodes based on the topology control mechanism to overcome the void regions. GEDAR improves the performance of system in various process of network compactness and traffic load. Hence, this protocol achieves the energy efficient is better when compared to the existing protocols of UWSN. GEDAR protocol should improve in topology mechanisms of depth adjustment principles and should consider in QoS requirements like cost of nodes, data delivery and network lifetime.

F. PBDTP (Prediction Based Delay-Tolerant Protocol)

Owing to the physical characteristics of the associated underwater acoustic channel[15], the propagation speed of the associated acoustic signal is significantly slower than that of a terrestrial radio wave. The channel will be affected by this huge delay. There are terribly high delays in the types of economical procedures. There are distinctive difficulties. The inconsistent delay is making some old communications protocols skimpy, since between 2 communication nodes they think about the right estimates of the travel time (RTT). Underwater networks with affiliation interruptions are inherently unreliable. By predicting a price for a device node, the PBDTP Protocol tolerates long delays, non-consistent delays and affiliation disruptions if the information was not received at the sink node instead of the device node being transmitted. The PBDTP reduces the traffic of information via networks and efficiently uses the network resource. The optimal and characteristics of the mobility pattern can not be found in this protocol. The minimum delay in delivery should be increased with low energy use in order to obtain PBDTP.

G. PASR (Prediction Assisted Single-copy Routing Protocol)

Efficient routing is a major challenge in delay tolerant networks (DTNs). Many current DTN protocols have two restrictions: certain protocols are not appropriate for mobility patterns, and some protocols use multi-copy copies for mobility, resulting in delay reduction but not working in all resource networks. PASR (Prediction Aided Single-Copy Routing) scheme is used to achieve delay distribution at low energy consumption and effectively using single-copy mobility pattern routing[16]. In PASR, a greedy algorithm is used to find mobile pattern's optimal properties and characteristics. Often labeled ACPG (Aggressive Chronological Projected Graph). Using ACPG, it will require preceding the design to get the specific historical information and forwarding strategy based on heuristic protocols. Single-routing systems EEHPA (Energy Efficient History Assisted Routing) and iEEHPA (improved Energy Efficient History Assisted Routing) were used for various mobility patterns for UWSN. PASR captures different mobility patterns and provides different schemes during simulation testing. It could improve performance for different batch intervals and use prediction methods, and finally PASR will extend mobility patterns to different DTNs.

2.2. HYBRID-BASED ROUTING PROTOCOLS

Energy efficiency is the broad issue in UWSN and the basic requirement is to achieve the longer network lifetime. Sensor node communication and transmission is not balanced so it results in high energy consumption. Using multi-hop communication and direct transmission it reduces and balanced the energy in sensor nodes. But the direct transmission through sensor nodes results more energy consumption. For this, hybrid-based routing protocols avoid the direct transmission from sensor to sink node [15]. This type of protocols divides into region and form a semicircular shape to deploy on the surface of water. The main focuses on this type of protocols is to find out the distance of direct transmission and achieves the energy efficiency.

A. QELAR (Q-learning-based Energy-Efficient and Lifetime-Aware Routing Protocol)

The biggest obstacle to develop UWSN networking protocols is inflated latency, limited bandwidth, and inflated energy usage. QELAR intends to improve network life using MAC protocols and sensor node residual resources. Residual energy has factored each sensor node and distributes one of them to determine the incentive function. Compared to the VBF protocol, QELAR gains 20% more lifetime[17]. Will sensor node must recognize and know the environment by selecting the next hop to share metadata information. This procedure doesn't restrict end-to - end delay[18]. And then QELAR 's long pause results inefficiently in certain setting.

QDAR (Q-learning dependent delay-aware routing)[19] is used to expand UWSN lifetime. This algorithm focuses primarily on complex climate. Big contributors are,

- a) Data collection process is specified and packet construction is built to easily route decisions to the complex underwater environment.
- b) It defines two cost function factors: delay-related costs and energy-related costs.
- c) It defined maintaining longer network existence and shorter delays.

It is easily extendable by energy consumption, channel capacity and other metrics.

Figure2. Total Power Consumption between QDAR and QELAR with different MAC protocols

Finally, QDAR calculation contrasts and QELAR and VBF results shows that it reduces the total power consumption and reduce the latency by 20-25%. Hence, QDAR is acceptable for time-critical applications.

A. TSR (Time-Slot-based protocol)

UWSN used the most efficient network technologies to achieve energy efficiency. TSR is one of the network strategies for implementing a set of flooding protocol considerations. TSR technology was developed to maximize energy efficiency and prolong network existence through a likelihood based system named TSBR. TSR's key objective is to save time dependent on flood protocol[20]. The protocol design defines UWSN's routing protocol:

Design TSR:

Basic TSR integrates the system for splitting the cycle of linking a route tree into a sink and regular route structure. The sink of the path establishment was processed and a transmitted path packet was submitted, and it eventually awaits the sink of target.

Figure 3. Process of establishing a route tree (a) Sink sends broadcast packet (b) Send broadcast packet-First layer (c) Send broadcast packet – Second layer (d) Established route tree

TSR maintains two tables for tracking this routing information: (a.) State table – contains residual energy, total packet size, power, error rates, delay average and how many time reports submit. (B.) Destination Table – Contains destination address, next hop date , and time by (route).

The TSR algorithm provides clear communication across the UWSN path. Any causes such as channel clashes, noise jamming, etc. triggered failure circumstances. To manage this issue, TSR divides into two categories and offers the best two methods to resolve: (1) node resolution system died (2) packet missing resolution method.

Design TSBR:

Fair likelihood approach is used to align network and maximize network lifespan. According to the equal probability principle, the route tree model changes the number of sub-nodes of each route tree to match probability. Therefore, it helps in stopping nodes wasting their resources and will absorb growing node 's energy depending on the network. This network protocol will extend lifespan. Network coding theory was introduced in the TSBR algorithm where results show that it eliminates node disputes, shortens development times, regulates the energy consumption of each node and prolongs network life[20].

B. E-PULRP (Energy-Optimized Path Unaware Layered Routing Protocol)

Conventional routing protocols are not suitable for UWSN due to high propagation delay, uncontrolled node location variations, network topology variation and connectivity loss due to underwater currents. PULRP (Path Ignorant Layered Protocol) was used to spread 3D-UWSN uniform sensor nodes and 2D UWSN uniform sensor nodes[21]. This protocol fails to provide effective energy in routing system architecture because node transmitting range could not be configured. It ends in energy consumption node failure[22].

E-PULRP was used to find the tightly configured 3D UWSN for standardized sensor nodes. Using this method, sink node was placed at the middle of deployment range, so growing node tracks range and reports events to the sink node. And then the sink node interacts with surface station info.

E-PULRP algorithm has two phases : (1) Layering Process – a series of clustered layers built around the sink node, meaning that the packet is routed straight to sink nodes. (2) Coordination process – choosing intermediate

relay nodes from source to sink (destination) for packet forwarding. Finally, it named future nodes. Two of the big achievements,

- a. Using this on-the-fly algorithm creation for 3D-UWSN.
- b. Throughput and end-to - end latency is evaluated.
- c. For node densities, an output limit was determined and packet forwarding assumptions were rendered for traffic conditions.

Therefore, E-PULRP achieves energy optimization by choosing UWSN's right communication parameters. This defines the statistical system and analyzes the output indicators. For efficient packet transmission, E-PULRP offers a traffic restriction the network can avoid. This protocol was quite simple, even without routing tables, localization techniques and other techniques[22]. This technique often prevents floods with one relay in each sheet.

Figure 4. Typical System architecture of E-PULRP model

C. H^n -PERP (Hop by Hop Power Efficient Routing Protocol)

One of the main challenges in UWSN is not efficiently delivering the data due to the weakness of acoustic transmission. H^n -PERP (Hop by Hop Power Efficient Routing Protocol) algorithm provides a mechanism control for expressing long-term data forwarding sensor networks. H^n -PERP is a routing protocol is to achieve more characterised by scheduling based on neighbour count, time, congestion and residual energy as on H2-DAB mechanism. It enhances the network throughput and energy efficiency depends on power monitoring in UWSN nodes by using centralized full control model (H^n -PERP) [23].

H^n -PERP provides secure mechanism for scheduling and processing information transmission supported variety of nodes, energy state and congestion among every node to reduce energy levels or power consumption by avoiding disconnected likelihood for any node that successfully increased the network time period. Different parameters involved in routing scheduling to improve the performance level and design of adaptive addressing which include power consumption and throughput over the network will be increased. The results show that this model is consistent with energy level and congestion and for enabling routing and data transmission.

D. L2-ABF (Layer-by-Layer Angle Based Flooding)

UWSN's biggest task is to have improved coordination and improve contact efficiency due to the unpredictable underwater environment. L2-BAF (Layer-by - Layer Angle Based Flooding) tackles problems of progressive node flow, beginning to end latency, and energy consumption[24]. To forward data packets to the sink, each node calculates the flood angle without specific setup or location information.

Too many routing methods have been applied over the last decade and rely on different network configuration and equipment. Some routing techniques needed sensor node position knowledge. L2-BAF routing protocol requires no local sensor node data and does not depend on any special setup and hardware. It is also stated the very useful angle measurement for flooding data packets and should not retain complicated routing chart. This protocol is to that the UWSN horizontal contact between sensor nodes at the same depth point. Using Angle-based flooding design to achieve this goal.

Figure 5. L2-ABF Angle Based Flooding Architecture

The main idea of L2-BAF is that the data delivery ratios are not actually affected while increasing the density of the sensor nodes. Finally, it can achieve high delivery ratio more than 90% for dense networks with small delays.

E. LB-AGR (Level Based Adaptive Geographic Routing)

The great challenge of UWSN is to develop the protocol design for energy-consumption and long-propagation delay that adopts acoustic communications. LB-AGR routing protocol provides the best solution in terms of energy consumption, throughput and delivery rate [25]. This protocol defines that each sensor node follows integrated forwarding factor build on energy available, degree of compactness, location, and the difference level between neighbour nodes and results the best next hop among multiple sensor nodes [26].

F. EEDBR (Energy-Efficient Depth-based Routing)

Improvising network lifespan is one of UWSN's biggest obstacles. The network protocol will be configured for energy consumption to enhance network life. The main factor in improving network existence is managing energy usage among other sensor nodes. The transmission number must be reduced to reduce energy consumption. To do this, EEDBR conducts energy balancing and boosts network existence to the the number of sensor nodes[27]. In EEDBR, the data packet is transmitted from source to sink by choosing the nodes based on depth and residual capacity. The cycle continues,

- a. Each sender transmits the data packet including a neighbor's ID list (consider just smaller depth).
- b. Selected nodes can forward the data packet.

- c. Sensor nodes keep the packet sometime until forwarding (holding period is dependent on sensor node residual energy).
- d. Sensor nodes were contrasting residual energy with strong residual energy forwards the package. Although low-energy nodes were violently terminated with the same file.
- e. Finally, the energy balance is achieved and the sensor nodes use their electricity parallel due to energy conservation, and the sensor node battery is fully utilized faster than others. Enhanced average network lifespan.

EEDBR contributes performance improvements such as lifespan, energy consumption, end-to - end latency and delivery ratio. All these considerations were contrasted to the other routing protocols and thus EEDBR shows UWSN 's strongest performance routing protocol[28].

3. SUMMARIZATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENT ROUTING PROTOCOLS

This section provides the review of energy efficiency routing protocols for UWSNs (Table 1). It is mainly focused on techniques, requirements and other characteristics of various protocols.

Protocol	Requirements	Energy Efficiency	Single / Multisink	Energy efficiency technique	Time Synchronization	Routing void detection	Routing Update
DBR	Depth information	Yes	Multisink	Greedy approach	No	No	Partial Update
iAMCTD	Depth information	Yes	Single	F _{FS} technique	No	No	Periodical Update
MRP	Zone of reference	Yes	Multisink	Apple slice	No	Yes	Partial Update
H2DAB	Location information	Yes	Multisink	Based on node movements	No	No	Periodical Update
GEDAR	Depth information	Yes	Multisink	Greedy approach	No	Yes	Full Update
PBDTP	Depth information	Yes	Single	Based on delay node	No	No	Full Update
PASR	Depth information	Yes	Single	Greedy approach	No	Yes	Partial Update
QELAR	Depth information	Yes	Single	MAC Protocols	No	No	Partial Update
TSR	Depth information	Yes	Multisink	Equal probability method	Yes	Yes	Periodical Update
E-PULRP	Location information	Yes	Multisink	<i>On the fly algorithm</i>	No	No	Full Update
Hn-PERP	Location information	Yes	Single	Power monitoring	No	No	Full Update
L2-ABF	Depth information	Yes	Multisink	Angle calculation	No	No	Full Update
LB-AGR	Location information	Yes	Single	Forwarding factor	No	Yes	Partial Update
EEDBR	Depth information	Yes	Single	Forwarding factor	No	Yes	Full Update

Table 1. Characteristics of different energy efficiency routing protocols in UWSNs

4. CONCLUSION

Underwater sensor networks (UWSNs) have unique characteristics, so the conventional routing protocols in terrestrial wireless sensor networks expose many drawbacks in UWSNs. In this paper, energy efficiency routing techniques were exploited to increase the lifetime of network environment and energy consumption. The paper may helpful for the researchers who are interested to focus on different routing protocols to achieve energy efficiency in UWSNs.

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